

Optimal Sizing and Energy Management of Battery Energy Storage Systems for Hybrid Offshore Farms

Sofia Varotto^{1,2,3}, Vincenzo Trovato^{1,4}, Ehsan Kazemi-Robati², Bernardo Silva^{2,3}

¹*Dept. of Civil, Environmental and Mechanical Engineering, University of Trento, Trento, Italy*

²*Center of Power and Energy Systems, INESC TEC, Porto, Portugal*

³*Faculty of Engineering, University of Porto, Porto, Portugal*

⁴*Dept. of Electrical and Electronic Engineering, Imperial College London, London, United Kingdom*

Abstract—This paper investigates the financial benefits stemming from the potential installation of battery energy storage systems behind the meter of a hybrid offshore farm including wind turbines and floating photovoltaic panels. The optimal investment and operation decisions concerning the energy storage system in the hybrid site are assessed by means of a mixed integer linear programming optimization model. The operation is also subject to technical constraints such as limitations on the connection capacity and ramping constraints imposed by the grid operator at the point of common coupling. Three design configurations for the battery system are analysed: I) offshore with the hybrid farm, II) onshore where the grid connection point is, III) both offshore and onshore. The results indicate the financial value of installing battery storage units, and other benefits deriving from this investment, as the reduction of curtailment.

I. INTRODUCTION

THE RECENT strive towards decarbonisation has led to an increase in the share of electricity production supplied by renewable energy sources (RES). Despite clear environmental benefits, their massive integration may concern RES plants owners due the intrinsic variability and uncertainty of RES power output. In this context, hybrid RES farms are attracting a growing interest, as the combination of different RES, e.g. wind and photovoltaic (PV) generation, at the same connection point appears to have potential advantages. Besides the possibility to share the same converter and connection capacity, a hybrid RES plant can benefit from the possible complementarity of the availability of the different sources. For instance, this may reduce the seasonal variability of the overall power output of the farm. Nonetheless, even hybrid RES plants are affected by the inability to perfectly forecast the short-term power output. For this reason, energy storage systems (ESS) can still be appealing for such farms as they are expected to smoothen the power output and overcome limitations on the connection capacity.

Recently, hybrid farms are becoming object of many studies, aiming at assessing their benefits respect to one-RES plants. In this sense, the sizing of a hybrid PV-wind plant in Jordan in [1], aiming at minimizing the costs, resulted in optimal configurations involving both RESs. [2] observed a smoothening of the power output due to the combination on wind and wave energy generation in the same offshore farm. The study from [3] had the purpose of finding the configuration of a

hybrid offshore farm comprising wind turbines and floating photovoltaics (FPV) that minimizes the seasonal variability, in terms of need for energy storage. The optimization results in a 40 – 45% PV share over the total hybrid park capacity. A more efficient utilization of connection assets has been proven in the model in [4] that assesses the triple combination of wind, wave and PV production in an offshore farm, resulting in a higher utilization factor of the transmission cable and less low-production hours in a year. The feasibility of the addition of FPV panels to an existing offshore wind farm, connected to shore through the preexisting cable, was proved by [5], and the benefits in terms of cable capacity factor were observed.

Different technologies of energy storage assets have proved potential benefits helping RES coping with their intrinsic variability and uncertainty. For example, in [6], the benefits stemming from the addition of storage technologies - working on different time scales - to an offshore wind farm were assessed. The design of a battery energy storage system (BESS) was optimized for different types of batteries in [7], also considering the uncertainty and the wake effect characterizing the power production of a wind farm. In [8], an optimal energy storage management improved the reliability of the RES production, resulting in a higher penetration of such sources in the electric grid. Hydrogen systems are also attracting considerable interest as means of energy storage from renewable farms, particularly wind: for instance, [9] studied the possibility to obtain a constant power output over a year from a wind turbine equipped with electrolyzer, storage and fuel cell. Similarly, [10] considered the case of a base load provision by a renewable-only system, namely wind and PV, with hydrogen and BESS.

The work in [11] presented a thorough outline of the most suitable energy storage technologies for offshore renewable farms, and an evaluation and ranking of the features that make them convenient for such application. Batteries, hydrogen, and, even more, their combination, result as the best options. An accurate model of an offshore wind farm equipped with BESS and hydrogen production was introduced by [12] to optimize the design and energy management of the system, resulting in a configuration including both types of storage. Also [13] presented a similar optimization, including also fuel cells for hydrogen re-conversion into electric power and interesting sensitivity analyses to evaluate different scenarios.

This paper contributes to existing literature concerning the integration of energy storage systems to offshore hybrid farms. Particular attention is devoted to highlight the potential advantages of BESS overcoming connection constraints to the shore. Furthermore, to the best of the authors' knowledge, this is the first study assessing whether it is more convenient to place the BESS onshore, offshore or both with respect to an offshore hybrid farm. This study is carried out as an optimization aiming at maximizing the economic benefits of installing BESSs. The work considers the offshore wind farm Alpha Ventus [14] located in the Northern Sea, near the island of Borkum. Hybrid farm scenarios are formed adding different levels of FPV capacity to the existing wind park.

The rest of this paper is organized as follows: in section II, the modelling features of each asset and the details of the optimization problem formulation are presented; the input data and results of the simulations are displayed and then discussed in section III. Finally, conclusions are drawn in section IV.

II. MATHEMATICAL MODEL

The hybrid farm and the BESS are modelled as in figure 1. Both the wind turbines and PV panels are located in the sea and connected to the shore by means of a submarine cable. The location of the BESS comprehends three possible distinct configurations: offshore (case I), onshore (case II) and both onshore and offshore at the same time (case III). The farm and the BESS are then connected to the grid at the point of common coupling (PCC), that is considered onshore in this study. The battery packs are connected to the system using AC/DC converters.

The mathematical modelling of the assets and the overall optimization problem is described in the following subsections.

Fig. 1: Schematic of the studied hybrid park assisted with BESSs.

A. Wind Power Production

The power output of each of the wind turbines, represented as P_{wt} (MW), is obtained as follows, and it is function of the wind velocity [1].

$$P_{wt}(k) = \begin{cases} 0 & \text{for } 0 \leq v(k) \leq v_{ci} \\ \frac{1}{2} c_P \rho_a A_{wt} \eta_{wt} v(k)^3 & \text{for } v_{ci} < v(k) \leq v^{rated} \\ P_{wt}^{rated} & \text{for } v^{rated} < v(k) \leq v^{co} \\ 0 & \text{for } v(k) > v^{co} \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

Where:

- $v(k)$ (m/s) is the wind velocity at the hub height, assumed uniform along the entire rotor area. $k \in \{1, N\}$ indicates the hour of the year being $N = 8760$.

- v_{ci}, v^{rated} and v^{co} (m/s) are respectively the cut in, rated and cut off wind speeds of the turbine.
- c_P is the power coefficient of the wind turbine.
- ρ_a (kg/m^3) is the air density, considered uniform.
- A_{wt} (m^2) is the rotor area.
- η_{wt} is the electrical efficiency of the turbine.
- $P_{wt}^{rated} = 5MW$ is the rated power of the wind turbine.

The maximum possible hourly power output of the whole farm is therefore calculated as:

$$P_w^{max}(k) = n_{wt} \cdot P_{wt}(k) \quad (2)$$

The particular wind farm considered in the proposed work is such that the number of turbines is $n_{wt} = 12$.

B. Photovoltaic Power Production

Different configurations with additional FPV installed power ranging up to 60MW are considered. Regardless of the actual installed power, the power output of the FPV panels $P_{pv}^{max}(k)$ (MW) is calculated as in [15] through the equation:

$$P_{pv}^{max}(k) = A_{pv} \cdot \eta_{pv} \cdot G(k) \cdot 10^{-6} \quad (3)$$

Where:

- A_{pv} (m^2) is the total area of the FPV panels.
- η_{pv} is the panel efficiency.
- $G(k)$ (W/m^2) is the surface net solar irradiance at the hour k .

C. Hybrid Farm

The variable P_f (MW), which is the actual power output of the farm, is subject to the constraint:

$$0 \leq P_f(k) \leq P_w^{max}(k) + P_{pv}^{max}(k) \quad (4)$$

The difference between $P_f(k)$ and the maximum power output $P_w^{max}(k) + P_{pv}^{max}(k)$ is the curtailed power $P_{curt}(k)$ (MW). From this point, the power output of the farm will not be distinguished between the one generated by the FPV panels and the one by the wind turbines, therefore it is not specified which RES will be subject to curtailment.

D. Battery System

The BESSs, both onshore and offshore, are composed of a number of individual battery cells that are represented $s_{b,on}$ and $s_{b,off}$ respectively, and an AC/DC converter. The nominal capacity of the batteries is $E_{b,cell}^{rated} = 4.8kWh$ and the C-rate is 1. The overall roundtrip efficiency of the battery system is $\eta_b = \eta_c^2$ where $\eta_c = 0.95$ is the efficiency of the AC/DC converter, both for charging and discharging. In the following description of the BESS, the modelling of both onshore and offshore systems will be explained using the generic subscript $x \in \{on, off\}$ for both onshore and offshore BESSs. The power input and output of the system is respectively $P_{b,x,in}$ and $P_{b,x,out}$ (MW), and the size of the battery pack is subject to the constraints:

$$P_{b,x,in}(k) \cdot \eta_c \leq s_{b,x} \cdot P_{b,cell}^{rated} \quad (5)$$

$$P_{b,x,out}(k)/\eta_c \leq s_{b,x} \cdot P_{b,cell}^{rated} \quad (6)$$

Where $P_{b,cell}^{rated}$ (MW) is the rated power of a single battery cell. The converter is sized using its rated power $P_{c,x}^{rated}$ according to:

$$P_{c,x}^{rated} = s_{b,x} \cdot P_{b,cell}^{rated} / \eta_c \quad (7)$$

The energy balance of the battery cell is expressed by the following equation, where $E_{b,x}$ (MWh) is the energy inside of the battery system:

$$E_{b,x}(k+1) = E_{b,x}(k) - [P_{b,x,out}(k) / \eta_c - P_{b,x,in}(k) \cdot \eta_c] \Delta_t \quad (8)$$

Where Δ_t is the time step of 1h. The minimum allowable state of charge of the batteries is considered to be 20% [10], therefore $E_{b,x}$ is constrained by:

$$s_{b,x} \cdot 20\% E_{b,cell}^{rated} \leq E_{b,x}(k) \leq s_{b,x} \cdot E_{b,cell}^{rated} \quad (9)$$

Furthermore, the energy inside the BESS is forced to be the same at the beginning and at the end of the considered year through the constraint:

$$E_{b,x}(N) = E_{b,x}(1) \quad (10)$$

E. Grid Connection

The cable connecting the farm to shore has a nominal power capacity of $P_{cable} = 62MW$ [16] as it was sized to transport the installed wind power of the farm: $P_w^{rated} = 60MW$. The following constraint is applied only to the offshore BESS:

$$P_f(k) - P_{b,off,in}(k) + P_{b,off,out}(k) \leq P_{cable} \quad (11)$$

Where $P_g(k)$ (MW) the power injected into the grid. At the PCC, it is supposed that the system operator applies a limitation for the power ramping of 10% of the overall capacity of the existing RES units [12], modelled as:

$$|P_g(k+1) - P_g(k)| \leq 10\% P_w^{rated} \quad (12)$$

Finally, at the PCC, the power balance is expressed as:

$$P_g(k) = P_f(k) - P_{b,off,in}(k) + P_{b,off,out}(k) - P_{b,on,in}(k) + P_{b,on,out}(k) \quad (13)$$

The flow of energy is unidirectional from the park into the grid and is constrained using:

$$P_g(k) \geq 0 \quad (14)$$

F. Optimization Problem

The optimization study is modelled as a MILP problem in which all variables are linear except for the numbers of batteries that are integer. The objective function that is maximized by the optimizer is the net present value (NPV) of the project, calculated over the farm's assumed lifetime that is $L_f = 25$ years, considering the same revenues and operation costs in all years during the study horizon. The NPV is defined as:

$$NPV = -C_i + \sum_{y=1}^{L_f} \frac{R(y) - R_{ns}(y) - C_o(y) - C_r(y)}{(1+i)^y} \quad (15)$$

Where:

- C_i (€) is the investment cost of the battery system, considering battery cells and converter. It is calculated as $C_i = s_{b,x} \cdot E_{b,cell}^{rated} \cdot U_{c,i,b} + P_{c,x}^{rated} \cdot U_{c,i,c}$, being $U_{c,i,b}$ and $U_{c,i,c}$ the unit cost of investment of the battery cells (€/kWh) and the converter (€/kW), respectively.
- $R(y) = \sum_{k=1}^N p_{el}(k) \cdot P_g(k)$ (€) are the revenues coming from the sale of electricity to the energy market along the year y , $p_{el}(k)$ (€/MWh) is the electricity price at the hour k ; $R_{ns}(y)$ are the yearly revenues of the farm without storage system and are subtracted from this calculation, to consider only the profit coming from the installation of the BESS itself.
- C_o (€/year) is the operation and maintenance cost of the battery system, calculated as $C_o = s_{b,x} \cdot E_{b,cell}^{rated} \cdot U_{c,o,b} + P_{c,x}^{rated} \cdot U_{c,o,c}$, being $U_{c,o,b}$ and $U_{c,o,c}$ the unit cost of operation per year for of the battery cells (€/MWh · year) and the converter (€/(MW · year)), respectively.
- C_r (€) is the replacement cost of the battery cells, being $C_r(y) = s_{b,x} \cdot E_{b,cell}^{rated} \cdot U_{c,i,b}$ for $y/10 \in \mathbb{N}$, $C_r(y) = 0$ otherwise.
- $i = 5\%$ is the interest rate.

G. Supplementary Indicators

In this subsections some other parameters and indicators are calculated, as they will be useful to display some of the outputs of the simulations. Firstly, the normalized size of the BESS, NSB_x (*n. of battery cells/MW*) is defined, in order to have comparable values regardless of the size of the farm, that is increasing with the addition of FPV.

$$NSB_x = \frac{s_{b,x}}{P_f^{max}} \quad (16)$$

Where \bar{P}_f^{max} (MW) is the average of the maximum power output of the farm, calculated as:

$$\bar{P}_f^{max} = \frac{\sum_{k=1}^N [P_w^{max}(k) + P_{pv}^{max}(k)]}{N} \quad (17)$$

Another useful indicator is the avoided curtailment AC (%), defined as:

$$AC = \frac{\sum_{k=1}^N [P_{curt,ns}(k) - P_{curt}(k)] \cdot \Delta_t}{AEP^{max}} \quad (18)$$

Where $P_{curt,ns}$ (MW) is the power that would be curtailed in the same farm configuration but without any BESS, and AEP^{max} (MW) is the maximum annual energy production achievable by the farm, calculated as:

$$AEP^{max} = \sum_{k=1}^N [P_w^{max}(k) + P_{pv}^{max}(k)] \cdot \Delta_t \quad (19)$$

Two indices of the variability of the power output into the grid are calculated from the optimal values obtained for P_g . The first one, called Absolute Variability Index (AVI) of the power output, is computed according to [17], as:

$$AVI = \sum_{k=2}^N |P_g(k) - P_g(k-1)| \quad (20)$$

From this index, a similar factor is proposed in this study, that allows to picture the variability of the power output while being comparable regardless of the production capacity of the farm. This index is called Coefficient of Absolute Variability of Power (CAVP) and is defined as:

$$CAVP = \frac{\sum_{k=2}^N |P_g(k) - P_g(k-1)|}{(N-1) \cdot \bar{P}_g} \quad (21)$$

Where \bar{P}_g is the mean power output to the grid over the year.

III. RESULTS

A. Input Data

The hourly wind speed and solar radiation data is taken from Copernicus Era5 reanalysis [18], and the electricity spot market prices for Germany from Ember [19], both from the year 2021. The data from this year is applied in this study in order to take into account the recent rising of electricity prices but avoiding the exceptional peaks reached in 2022.

The unit costs of the components of the BESS and their lifetimes are reported in table I:

Component	Lifetime years	$U_{c,i}$	$U_{c,o}$ % of $U_{c,i}$
Battery	10 [13]	183 €/kWh [20]	1%/year [12]
Converter	25 [13]	243 €/kW [20]	2%/year [12]

TABLE I: Components data.

It should be noted that 1% for C_o of the battery cells is a rounding of $\frac{C_o}{C_i}$ (%) used in [12] in the cost data of lithium batteries, whereas 2% for the converter is the same ratio used in [12].

B. Simulation Results

MATLAB Optimization Toolbox is used to solve this MILP optimization problem. The simulations have been implemented for five different configurations of the additional FPV power: 0%, 25%, 50%, 75% and 100% of the previously installed wind power - corresponding to 0, 15, 30, 45 and 60 MW of FPV. These five configurations were studied for the three different storage location scenarios of case I, II and III. The possible additional costs of installing batteries on an offshore platform compared to onshore were neglected for simplicity.

The first simulation output to be analyzed is the optimal size of the BESS, in absolute terms (Fig. 2) and normalized (Fig. 3), meaning divided by \bar{P}_f^{max} as explained in subsection II-G. As indicated in Fig. 2, the sizing of the BESS under the onshore-only configurations (case II) results to be larger than under the offshore-only configuration (case I). This is due to the fact that the onshore BESS can contribute to increment the amount of energy exchanged to the grid during hours characterized by high electricity prices without being subject to limitation introduced by the rated capacity (62 MW) of the cable. The economic value arising from this operational paradigm balances the investment cost due to a higher number of battery cells. Nonetheless, the split placement of the BESS in case III, onshore and offshore, is more economically effective and convenient than the other two. As an example

for the 30 MW additional PV configuration, the NPV for the case I, II and III are displayed in table II:

Case	NPV (M€)
I	3.722
II	3.701
III	3.776

TABLE II: Net present value of BESS installation for 30 MW additional PV power.

On the one hand, the share of offshore batteries contributes to the reduction in the RES energy curtailment driven by the cable limitation. On the other hand, the onshore batteries boost the overall profits by taking advantage of the price differentials of the wholesale market.

Fig. 2: Optimal sizes of the storage systems, as number of battery cells.

Overall, it is clear that the size of the installed BESS increases along with the integration of PV capacity in all cases. Furthermore, results concerning the normalized trends in Fig. 3 suggest that the lowest amount of BESS capacity occurs when the additional PV capacity is 30 MW i.e. 50% of the wind installed capacity.

Fig. 3: Optimal sizing of the storage systems, in terms of number of battery cells normalized by \bar{P}_f^{max} .

Fig. 4, concerning case III, displays the number of batteries installed onshore and the ones installed offshore. The graph shows that the share of onshore BESS is higher when the PV capacity is 0, while it decreases as the RES installed capacity

exceeds the cable limitation. When the PV installed capacity reaches its maximum value, the number of batteries onshore and the number of batteries offshore are almost equal.

Fig. 4: Optimal sizing of the storage systems in case III, in terms of number of battery cells.

Economic benefit is selected as objective function of this optimization, in order to consider the practical feasibility of storage installation from the point of view of an investor. However, other parameters that are not related to the economic return can be observed. For instance, the reduction in the RES curtailment is one of the desired benefits from BESS. Hence, Fig. 5 displays the avoided RES curtailment thanks to the installation of BESS, calculated as in 18. Notably, the avoided curtailment levels are generally very similar among all three cases. Nonetheless, it is worth highlighting some observations; without any extra PV capacity, the onshore BESS of case II leads to a higher percentage of avoided curtailment. Instead, when the additional PV capacity is above 30 MW, the offshore BESS becomes more efficient against the curtailment. This is due to the cable capacity becoming more restraining, therefore causing more curtailment, and this limitation cannot be effectively tackled by an onshore BESS. Case III tops the avoided curtailment of both the other cases, for any additional PV level.

Fig. 5: Avoided curtailment as percentage of AEP^{max} .

The indices calculated in 20 and 21 are displayed in Fig. 6 and 7 respectively. The results show that the variability indices of P_g are higher in case II. This is due to the fact that the power output can exceed the cable limitation of 62MW, even

more than in case III since all the batteries are onshore, and it is prone to do it when electricity prices are particularly high. For all cases, the absolute variability index increases along with the increase of the additional PV power, but the Coefficient of Absolute Variability firstly decreases and then slightly increases again at 100% additional PV. The difference in CAVP between case I and case II is higher for the 100% PV because of the higher optimal number of batteries that allows the power output of the onshore battery case to fluctuate more.

Fig. 6: Absolute variability index power injected into the grid.

Fig. 7: Coefficient of Absolute Variability of the power injected into the grid.

Finally, in order to visualize the power output to the grid P_g , together with P_f^{max} , they are shown in figure 8 over a sample week for case III. The electricity price is also displayed, to observe how it affects the energy management implemented through the BESS management and curtailment. In the second graph, the charging and discharging of the onshore and offshore BESSs are displayed.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

This paper presents a model for the optimal sizing and energy management of BESS for a hybrid wind-PV offshore farm, from the point of view of the economic return, considering different possible locations for the storage system. The outcome of this study highlights the benefits of the installation of a BESS; in particular it allows to effectively reduce RES curtailment and increases the profits stemming from the energy sale to the electricity network. Notably, the largest economic benefits are enabled when both onshore and offshore BESS allocation is applied. On the other hand, it is worth highlighting that the power output of the hybrid RES farm is less

Fig. 8: Power injected into the grid and power in and out from the BESS, onshore and offshore - positive for charging, negative for discharging - over a sample week, case III, 100% additional PV.

fluctuating when the BESS is located entirely offshore. The presented model can be applied to offshore parks of different capacity and including different RES technologies, such as wave energy converters. The accuracy of the model could improve in the future work by analysing the different costs and environmental impacts that the offshore installation of BESS might have compared to onshore. Further assessments will also be conducted on the addition of a hydrogen production system besides the BESS in the hybrid offshore park. This will increase the intrinsic flexibility of the entire hybrid plant.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

The research leading to this work is being carried out as a part of the EU-SCORES (European Scalable Complementary Offshore Renewable Energy Sources) project, European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme under grant agreement No 101036457. Views and opinions expressed are, however, those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

REFERENCES

- [1] H. Al-Masri and M. Ehsani, "Feasibility investigation of a hybrid on-grid wind photovoltaic retrofitting system," in *2015 IEEE Industry Applications Society Annual Meeting*, 2015, pp. 1–7.
- [2] J. M. Kluger, M. N. Haji, and A. H. Slocum, "The power balancing benefits of wave energy converters in offshore wind-wave farms with energy storage," *Applied Energy*, vol. 331, 2 2023.
- [3] E. Jonasson, O. Lindberg, D. Lingfors, and I. Temiz, "Design of wind-solar hybrid power plant by minimizing need for energy storage," 2023.
- [4] A. Schaap and H. V. der Zant, "Dimensioning and optimization of multi-source offshore renewable energy parks," *Proceedings of the European Wave and Tidal Energy Conference*, vol. 15, 9 2023.
- [5] S. Z. Golroodbari, D. F. Vaartjes, J. B. Meit, A. P. van Hoeken, M. Eberveld, H. Jonker, and W. G. van Sark, "Pooling the cable: A techno-economic feasibility study of integrating offshore floating photovoltaic solar technology within an offshore wind park," *Solar Energy*, vol. 219, pp. 65–74, 5 2021.
- [6] J. P. Barton and D. G. Infield, "Energy storage and its use with intermittent renewable energy," *Loughborough University, UK*, 2004.
- [7] S. Paul, A. P. Nath, and Z. H. Rather, "A multi-objective planning framework for coordinated generation from offshore wind farm and battery energy storage system," *IEEE Transactions on Sustainable Energy*, vol. 11, pp. 2087–2097, 10 2020.
- [8] A. Damiano, G. Gatto, I. Marongiu, M. Porru, and A. Serpi, "Real-time control strategy of energy storage systems for renewable energy sources exploitation," *IEEE Transactions on Sustainable Energy*, vol. 5, pp. 567–576, 2014.
- [9] J. Samaniego, F. Alija, S. Sanz, C. Valmaseda, and F. A. Frechoso Escudero, "Economic and technical analysis of a hybrid wind fuel cell energy system," *Renewable Energy*, vol. 33, pp. 839–845, 05 2008.
- [10] M. Hamdi, R. Ragab, and H. A. E. Salmawy, "The value of diurnal and seasonal energy storage in baseload renewable energy systems: A case study of Ras Ghareb – Egypt," *Journal of Energy Storage*, vol. 61, 5 2023.
- [11] Y. Arellano-Prieto, E. Chavez-Panduro, P. S. Rossi, and F. Finotti, "Energy storage solutions for offshore applications," *Energies*, vol. 15, 9 2022.
- [12] Z. Ma, T. Tian, Q. Cui, J. Shu, J. Zhao, and H. Wang, "Rapid sizing of a hydrogen-battery storage for an offshore wind farm using convex programming," *International Journal of Hydrogen Energy*, vol. 48, pp. 21 946–21 958, 7 2023.
- [13] F. Baldi, A. Coraddu, M. Kalikatzarakis, D. Jeleňová, M. Collu, J. Race, and F. Maréchal, "Optimisation-based system designs for deep offshore wind farms including power to gas technologies," *Applied Energy*, vol. 310, 3 2022.
- [14] Alpha Ventus offshore wind farm. [Online]. Available: <https://www.alpha-ventus.de/english>
- [15] C. Koroneos, A. Dompros, and G. Roumbas, "Renewable energy driven desalination systems modelling," *Journal of Cleaner Production*, vol. 15, pp. 449–464, 2007.
- [16] Tennet. [Online]. Available: <https://www.tennet.eu/projects/alpha-ventus>
- [17] F. Fusco, G. Nolan, and J. V. Ringwood, "Variability reduction through optimal combination of wind/wave resources - an irish case study," *Energy*, vol. 35, pp. 314–325, 1 2010.
- [18] Copernicus Era5 reanalysis. [Online]. Available: <https://cds.climate.copernicus.eu/cdsapp#!/dataset/reanalysis-era5-single-levels>
- [19] Ember. [Online]. Available: <https://ember-climate.org/data-catalogue/european-wholesale-electricity-price-data/>
- [20] W. Cole and A. Karmakar, "Cost projections for utility-scale battery storage: 2023 update," 2030. [Online]. Available: www.nrel.gov/publications.